

GENDER EQUALITY IN UZBEKISTAN.

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Abstract. *In order to further expand gender equality and women's opportunities, to promote systemic changes in the field, it is appropriate to change stereotypes and norms firmly established in society.*

Keywords: *gender equality, patriarchy, United Nations Population Fund (UNPF) "UN-Women".*

ГЕНДЕРНОЕ РАВЕНСТВО В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ.

Аннотация. *В целях дальнейшего расширения гендерного равенства и возможностей женщин, содействия системным изменениям в сфере целесообразно изменить устоявшихся в обществе стереотипов и норм.*

Ключевые слова: *гендерное равенство, патриархат, Фонд ООН в области народонаселения (UNPF) «ООН-женщины».*

INTRODUCTION

Gender equality and sexual equality, more precisely: equality between men and women, is a concept that implies the achievement of equal rights between men and women in the family and other legal relationships. According to some researchers, gender equality is the next stage of socio-sexual relations after the patriarchal system. The principle of gender equality is to study and eliminate all social barriers that prevent a person from emerging as a person, as well as to create equal social opportunities for realizing the personality of men and women in all spheres of life.

Uzbekistan began participating in the list of gender equality indicators from 2019. According to the status of 2019, the gender equality indicator of Uzbekistan took the 62nd place among 189 countries on the list. According to experts of the United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA), 29 women out of every 100,000 in Uzbekistan die due to gender inequality, and the birth rate for every thousand adolescent girls aged 15-19 is 23.8.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Along with Uzbekistan, Costa Rica and Uruguay are also on the 62nd place on the list of gender equality indicators with an indicator of 0.288. Among the countries of Central Asia, Kazakhstan ranks 44th, Kyrgyzstan 82nd, Tajikistan 70th, and Turkmenistan has no information on this list. According to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 23, 2022, the World Bank's "Women, Business and Law" index was included in the list of international rankings and indices of priority for the Republic of Uzbekistan, and the State Agency for Family and Women became the responsible state body for it. girls' state committee was established.

Today, the "Women, Business and Law" index covers 190 countries and includes 8 indicators (Freedom of movement, work, working conditions, marriage, parenthood, entrepreneurship, property ownership, pension). assesses the legal differences between men's and women's potential to use economic opportunities in the country.

Each indicator represents a separate stage in a woman's career. The methodology was developed as an easily reproducible measure of the legal environment for women as entrepreneurs and employees.

RESULTS

The index is updated based on feedback from respondents qualified in family, labor and criminal law. Currently, our country ranks 120th in the World Bank's "Women, Business and Law" index, scoring 70.6 points out of 100. In particular, to analyze the data and evaluation methodology of the World Bank's "Women, Business and Law" index for 2022 together with the interested agencies and organizations, to conduct an inventory of the NSCs adopted in this direction during 2021-2022, to analyze the data attention was drawn to the importance of issues of timely submission.

On September 2, 2019, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 562 "On guarantees of equal rights and opportunities for women and men" was adopted in Uzbekistan. The Gender Equality Commission has been operating in Uzbekistan since 2019. The Chairperson of the Senate of the Oliy Majlis Tanzila Narbaeva is the Chairperson of the Commission on Ensuring Gender Equality of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In 2015, a report was prepared by the United Nations Office on Gender Equality and Women's Empowerment in Pakistan. This report is known as "UN-Women". One of the central issues of the report was the issue of women's employment. According to the authors of the report, despite the fact that the number of women with higher education has reached a historical maximum, their employment situation looks sad. Young women who graduate with honors degrees, especially in subjects such as medicine and mathematics, cannot find work, despite the fact that they increasingly outstrip young men. Even those who manage to find a job do not always feel confident due to social insecurity. This issue is especially relevant in developing countries, where 75 percent of women's jobs are not protected by the employer's legal obligations.

Gender equality in the system of the Ministry of Public Education. Of the 6,119,440 students studying in the educational institutions of the Ministry of Public Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2,968,471 (48.5%) are girls. 332 of the 481,604 teaching staff working directly in the system 909 (69.1%) are women. If we talk about the number of women among the management staff in the system, there are 3689 (37.1%) of the existing 9925 school principals, 35 (17.5%) of the heads of public education departments of 200 districts (cities), this year In particular, 2 (14.2%) of the heads of public education departments of 14 regions are women.

DISCUSSION

In the Ministry of Public Education, a deputy minister responsible for women, gender equality and youth issues was appointed and a separate department was established, which is engaged in popularizing and improving best practices on these issues in the system. Also, the activities of the Women's Committee of Uzbekistan as leaders of primary organizations in all educational institutions, organizations, district (city) public education departments, regional public education management offices in the system of the Ministry of Public Education, including the central apparatus of the Ministry established. Currently, it is through them that the rights and opportunities of women in the system are widely promoted. Based on the experience of developed countries, the Ministry of Public Education inculcates the issues of gender equality in the minds of young people starting from school. It should be emphasized that equal conditions are created for girls and boys in all institutions.

As noted in the report, the situation of gender equality in developed countries is not far from the ideal level. For example, in Sweden and France, the difference in women's salaries compared to men is 31% less, in Germany it is 49% less, and in Turkey it is 75%. According to the authors of the report, the main measures to combat gender inequality are the right to provide women with good jobs around the world.

CONCLUSION

Critics of this concept state that the concept of equality is equal opportunities for all, citing the main postulates. Critics of the concept of gender equality consider it almost impossible because "men and women are different and not only physiologically but also mentally" and therefore "there can be no question" when it comes to "equality" because society. If men are forced to do the things that women love (going to the shops, buying clothes, decorating their faces with cosmetics, taking care of the children, cleaning the house), they cannot be happy. A woman, on the other hand, will not be happy if society forces her to do only men's work: chopping wood, repairing cars, driving a bulldozer. According to some sociologists, the mentality, behavioral motives and way of thinking are dominated by gender in modern society. Critics of the concept of equality, although they recognize the essence of the concept in general, give it another definition: Gender equality is the opportunity for a woman to develop as a woman, and a man as a man.

REFERENCES

1. *Kalabixina I. Ye.* Kratkiy ponyatiyniy slovar po gendernim issledovaniyam // Sotsialniy pol: ekonomicheskoe i demograficheskoe povedenie Uchebno-metodicheskie materialy po kursu. M., 1998.
2. ↑ Gender tenglik bo'yicha butunjahon statistikasi.
3. ↑ Gender tengligi ko'rsatkichi ro'yxati (PDF).
4. ↑ <https://lex.uz/docs/-4494849> Xotin-qizlar teng huquq kafolatlari to'g'risidagi O'RQ-562 02.09.2019
5. Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Article 46
6. Law "On guarantees of equal rights and opportunities for women and men", August 23, 2019